

Experiment Based Performance Evaluation of MongoDB and MySQL

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Abstract- With the increased demand of data availability it has become mandatory to look into the performance bottleneck of the traditional databases. In this paper we present a comprehensive setup to evaluate the performance of MySQL and MongoDB with respect to basic database operations on big data sets. It is found that as the record size goes beyond 10000 bytes, MongoDB outperforms MySQL.

Index Terms: MySQL, MongoDB, NoSQL, RDBMS, Big Data.

I. INTRODUCTION

In current times it is required that the applications that support millions of users must be up 24/7. And it must be able to handle thousands of simultaneous connections [1]. In addition to the number of simultaneous connections the corporations are required to handle millions of records i.e. huge volume of data, with very high speed and complexity. In such situations, the traditional Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS) face limitations as RDMS do not allow for a complete setup that may be tailored to meet specific requirements. Because of these constraints, non-relational databases often know as NoSQL(Not Only SQL) databases, have been developed[2]. Carlo Strozzi coined the term “No SQL” in 1998 to refer to such systems and Eric Evans revived it in 2009.

NoSQL is designed to meet the demands of modern applications that supports document data model, a distributed system architecture and a uniform interface that allows us to operate everywhere. The MongoDB 4.0 is the perfect solution for the challenges posed by the requirements [3], and therefore it is advisable to explore and test the MongoDB server for possible adoption.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section we present a brief overview of a RDBMS i.e. MySQL a NoSQL DBMS i.e. MongoDB Tauro et al. [4] gives a detailed comparison of agile, scalable and high performance NoSQL databases.

Wei-ping et al. showed that it is more advantageous to implement a textbook management system using MongoDB instead of MySQL [5].

Oracle DB and MongoDB both focus on document-oriented data storage. It is crucial to take into account the theoretical differences between the two. Baice et al. explore the features, limitations, integrity, distribution, system requirements, architecture, and query and insertion times of the two databases[6].

NoSQL databases and their key-value stores when paired with MapReduce provide an excellent foundation for collecting big data in efficient manner. This study along with read intensive versus write intensive tutorials is well presented by Bonnet et al. [7].

Due to programming errors or incomplete transactions, MapReduce programming paradigm may result in incorrect references. How to implement a verification technique for such a problem is the aim of the work by Georgiev [8]

Manoharan[9] did a comparison of SQL and NoSQL databases. Key value store solutions on both NoSQL and SQL databases are compared in this study. He discovered that not all NoSQL databases outperform a SQL database he evaluated for performance. He defines that even inside NoSQL databases, performance varies greatly depending on the operations performed on the data.

A detailed survey of relational and non – relational databases was presented by Jatana et al. [10]. A similar study was also conducted by Nayak et al. [11].

Performance analysis of NoSQL and

RDBMS was carried out by Bose and Abraham[12]. They performed their task using MySQL workbench and MongoDB studio 3T. They conclude that NoSQL databases outperform relational databases in all the scenarios studied.

Table 1 shows the main terms used in our experiment also.

TABLE 1

MySQL	MongoDB
Database	Database
Table	Collection
Index	Index
Row	BSON Document
Column	BSON Field
Join	Embedded documents and linking
Primary Key	Primary Key
Group by	Aggregation

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We installed MySQL server and MongoDB on Intel core i9 (3.3GHz), 128GB RAM and 1 TB SSD. The operating system used is Microsoft Windows 10 Ultimate 64-bit. We gathered the data over a period of two years from various organizations. We named down to 75 columns and 100 columns. We performed insert, select, update and delete operations.

Figure 1 shows MongoDB operations insert, select, update and delete based on 75 columns and Figure 2 shows these operations on 100 columns.

Figure 1. MongoDB: Compare Study of Insert, select (query), Update, Delete based on 75 columns

Figure 2. MongoDB: Compare Study of Insert, select (query), Update, Delete based on 100 Columns

Figure 3 shows MySQL operations insert, select, update and delete based on 75 columns and Figure 4 shows these operations on 100 columns.

Figure 3. MySQL: Compare Study of Insert, select (query), Update, Delete based on 75 Columns.

Figure 4. MySQL: Compare Study of Insert, select (query), Update, Delete based on 100 Columns.

MongoDB requires very little time than MySQL for inserting, updating, deleting, and selecting a huge record in the database in the insertion, selection, update, and delete operation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The performance of MySQL and MongoDB is compared using records and the time it takes to accomplish the operation. When there are less records, there is no difference in execution time between MongoDB and MySQL databases. As the number of records rises, MongoDB takes substantially less time to execute than MySQL. MongoDB outperforms MySQL in terms of performance when there are more records. In this regard, MongoDB is the better choice.

MongoDB is an excellent choice if you're looking for a quick, scalable database. If you don't care about the database's speed, and if you need to connect tables and collections, you may use MySQL or Oracle Databases.

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